

SUPERNOVA

Cybersecurity and grid-friendly Requirements /D5.1

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Introduction

1.1. Scope and Objectives

These guidelines are a tool that will underline many of the activities of the SUPERNOVA project related to the development of digitalised and connected tools and components for reliable and high performance PV systems. The Cybersecurity guidelines and grid-friendly requirements defined in this publication will also be crucial as the SUPERNOVA project looks to interconnect and hybridise these solutions and tools in order to improve the quality of insights available to asset managers as to the performance and O&M needs of their solar plants in a highly digitised system. Moreover, respecting strict cybersecurity best practices allows to preserve the integrity of solar power plant and connected technical systems (storage, local electricity network, transmission grids...) and of the resulting data. Increased interconnection of systems and data represents a tremendous potential for synergies, efficiency and new services, as cooperation around data sharing improves and Data Space enables to extract new insights from shared data. Proper use of cybersecurity best practices facilitates interaction and data sharing while reducing various risks from data theft to issues in systems operation.

The objectives of this publication is to define the cybersecurity requirements for technical tools developed within the SUPERNOVA project according to the state of the art of the market. This document will also provide an overview of the regulatory framework (current and upcoming) for cybersecurity in the photovoltaics sector in Europe, notably around the topic of data sharing, as well as deliver an overview of relevant existing standards for cybersecurity in PV, and potentials gaps and needs from the perspective of stakeholders in the PV sector.

1.2. Overview of relevant Innovations developed for the Supernova PV DATA Space

The IDSA¹ reference architecture model for data exchange offers an reference framework for establishing secure data exchange in a multiple-actor scenario such as the SUPERNOVA project. We therefore provide a short overview of its main components which will define the proposed data space for the SUPERNOVA project.

The IDSA reference architecture implementation is based on the following three core concepts (see also Figure 1):

Data sovereignty: Data providers have control over their data, even when it's being shared or utilized by third-party entities: in any practical implementation of the IDSA architecture, the data owner defines who can access their data, how long and for what purpose. Policies are put in place by the data provider and must be agreed by the data consumer before any download.

Decentralization: IDSA focuses on a decentralized approach for data exchange: data are not duplicated centrally, as done with more traditional data exchange mechanisms like cloud storage or web platforms. Moreover, each participant can take decisions based on their policies and business needs when they share data.

¹ International Data Spaces Association <https://internationaldataspaces.org/offers/reference-architecture/>

Connectors: They are the essential technical tools in the IDSA architecture and act as gateways for data exchange. Connectors implement the rules and policies set by data providers and ensure that data sovereignty is maintained. Data space connectors ensure end-to-end encryption of data during exchange. They allow dynamic and real-time data exchanges while providing data-specific access controls. Unlike web application tools like SharePoint, they are designed primarily for data exchange and ensure scalability and integration across diverse platforms.

Figure 1: Illustration of the core implementation concepts of the data space for the solar industry: Data sovereignty (represented by the broker agreement and the identity trust store), Decentralization (connectors are run locally by each part) and the connectors (the software layer that permits the data exchange)

SUPERNOVA aims at developing a data space for the PV sector with the following objectives:

- To create “apps” that apply on the PV data space differential privacy to generate publishable datasets and federated learning to maintain confidentiality while generating common insights.
- To open up to worldwide access to selected time series and images to develop algorithms and enable AI for digital PV.
- To develop good practices for the contractualization and monetization of data sharing (Asset Managers/Owners-O&M).

Cybersecurity plays a pivotal role in upholding data sovereignty and trust, which are foundational pillars in the successful deployment and scaling of data spaces. It is through the adoption of effective cybersecurity practices and technologies that data can be protected from a spectrum of threats, ensuring adherence to regulatory standards and, thus, cultivating a reliable environment for data transactions. This is particularly critical as it fosters synergies within the ever more interlinked data ecosystems.

2. Grid integration and Cyber Security (NIST Analysis)

Adhering to industry and regulatory best practices for IT security and demonstrating to paying attention to the standard health of the organization become necessary with the increasing of possible hardware/software vulnerabilities. **A cybersecurity framework** can support those necessities.

A cybersecurity framework provides **a common language** and set of standards for **security leaders across countries and industries** to understand their security postures and those of their customers and suppliers: it becomes much easier to define the processes and procedures that an organization must take to assess, monitor, and mitigate **cybersecurity risks**.

2.1. Three Most Common cybersecurity frameworks and standards

Appropriate cybersecurity frameworks and solutions will vary significantly across organizations depending on the industry, scale, and scope of the organization's operations. Which **security framework** is right for a given organization? Many questions must be answered to identify the relevant framework in which cybersecurity measures should be developed. For instance, the identification of potential regulations or a specific framework that a security program in a given industry would have to follow. To facilitate the identification of the right framework for PV stakeholders, among the most widely adopted cybersecurity model types, we have highlighted three of the most popular primary cybersecurity models that companies should follow to develop a mature cybersecurity program.

The **most Common Cybersecurity Model Types** are:

- **NIST**
- **ISO 27001**
- CIS 20
- HIPAA
- PCI-DSS
- **GDPR**

This chapter presents the main principles of **NIST**, **ISO27000** and **GDPR**. It also introduces the key differences and similarities between the two of them and the reason why for the **SCADA** trackers control systems the **NIST** is preferred.

2.2. NIST Cybersecurity Framework 2.0

NIST was established in response to an executive order by former President Obama — **Improving Critical Infrastructure Cybersecurity** — which called for greater collaboration between the public and private sector for identifying, assessing, and **managing cyber risk**.

Starting from this first target it has become the main standard for assessing **cybersecurity maturity**, identifying gaps and meeting **cybersecurity regulations**.

In 2024, NIST developed the new Cybersecurity Framework 2.0 (CSF2.0), updating the **CSF 1.1 produced in 2018**. This new framework is based on six core functions:

1. **Identify:** The organization's current cybersecurity risks are understood. Understanding the organization's assets (e.g., data, hardware, software, systems, facilities, services, people), suppliers, and related cybersecurity risks enables an organization to prioritize its efforts consistent with its risk management strategy and the mission needs identified under GOVERN. This Function also includes the identification of improvement opportunities for the organization's policies, plans, processes, procedures, and practices that support cybersecurity risk management to inform efforts under all six Functions.
2. **Protect:** Safeguards to manage the organization's cybersecurity risks are used. Once assets and risks are identified and prioritized, PROTECT supports the ability to secure those assets to prevent or lower the likelihood and impact of adverse cybersecurity events, as well as to increase the likelihood and impact of taking advantage of opportunities. Outcomes covered by this Function include identity management, authentication, and access control; awareness and training; data security; platform security (i.e., securing the hardware, software, and services of physical and virtual platforms); and the resilience of technology infrastructure.
3. **Detect:** Possible cybersecurity attacks and compromises are found and analyzed. DETECT enables the timely discovery and analysis of anomalies, indicators of compromise, and other potentially adverse events that may indicate that cybersecurity attacks and incidents are occurring. This function supports successful incident response and recovery activities.
4. **Respond:** Actions regarding a detected cybersecurity incident are taken. RESPOND supports the ability to contain the effects of cybersecurity incidents. Outcomes within this Function cover incident management, analysis, mitigation, reporting, and communication.
5. **Recover:** Assets and operations affected by a cybersecurity incident are restored. RECOVER supports the timely restoration of normal operations to reduce the effects of cybersecurity incidents and enable appropriate communication during recovery efforts.
6. **Govern:** The organisation's cybersecurity risk management strategy, expectations, and policy are established, communicated, and monitored. The GOVERN Function provides outcomes to inform what an organization may do to achieve and prioritize the outcomes of the other five Functions in the context of its mission and stakeholder expectations. Governance activities are critical for incorporating cybersecurity into an organization's broader enterprise risk management (ERM) strategy. GOVERN addresses an understanding of organizational context; the establishment of cybersecurity strategy and cybersecurity supply chain risk management; roles, responsibilities, and authorities; policy; and the oversight of cybersecurity strategy.

The journey from CSF 1.1 to CSF 2.0 represents NIST's commitment to evolving the security framework in response to the changing cybersecurity challenges and the needs of its users. Organizations are encouraged to customize the CSF to their specific contexts and share their experiences to benefit the broader community.

Figure 2: Evolution of the CSF1.1 into CSF2.0 (Source: NIST)

2.3. ISO 27001

Created by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) to fix best practices for information security management systems. This model is more popular among the EU based organizations. It focuses its attention on the three main areas of a mature cybersecurity management structure: people, process and technology.

The structure of the ISO27001 framework for cybersecurity emphasizes the following areas as focal point for the implementation of best cybersecurity practices to reach program maturity:

1. Security risk assessment
2. Security policy
3. Asset management
4. Human resources security
5. Physical and environmental security
6. Communications and operations management
7. Access control
8. Information systems acquisition, development, and maintenance
9. Information security incident management
10. Business continuity management

The ISO 27000 framework includes the management of critical physical and operational security measures and is broken down into ISO 27000 Series to get more specific into the actual implementation and design of this cybersecurity model.

ISO 27000 Series	
ISO27001	ISMS Requirements
ISO27002	ISMS controls
ISO27003	ISMS implementation guidelines
ISO27004	ISMS Measurements
ISO27005	Risk management
ISO27006	Guidelines for ISO 27000 accreditation bodies

Figure 3: Components of the ISO27000 framework for cybersecurity. A comprehensive programme should be consistent with all sub-component of the framework. (Source: ISO)

2.4. GDPR

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) is the European Union's (EU) personal data protection law that aims to protect the privacy of EU citizens. Enacted in May 2018, it imposes a unified set of rules on all organizations that process personal data originating from the EU, regardless of location.

The main target of the GDPR is to protect:

- *The personal data* used to identify a person as: names, identification numbers, location data, contact details (telephone – addresses), credit card numbers, account data;
- *Sensitive personal data*: genetic information, racial and ethnic data, political affiliations, religious affiliations or ideological convictions, trade union membership.

Since that the Data Protection is a core of both cybersecurity and GDPR compliance, it outlines six specific principles for companies in order to process and manage personal data:

1. Lawfulness, fairness, and transparency
2. Purpose limitation
3. Data minimization
4. Storage limitation
5. Integrity and confidentiality
6. Overarching accountability

One of the main principles of the GDPR **is that personal data gathered by the organization should only be accessible to employees who have a specific and critical need for that data as part of their day-to-day professional responsibilities.** This helps ensure that access to personally identifiable information (PII) and sensitive personal data is limited to as few people as possible.

Identity and access management (IAM) is a **framework** that allows the **IT team** to verify a user's identity and confirm their access rights. Though IAM is broadly applicable to any system, network or asset, in the context of the GDPR, IAM focuses on data access.

Within IAM, there are several secure access strategies organizations can consider, including:

Zero Trust: A security framework requiring all users, whether in or outside the organization's network, to be authenticated, authorized and continuously validated for security configuration and posture before being granted or keeping access to applications and data.

Principle of Least Privilege (POLP): A computer security concept and practice that gives users limited access rights based on the tasks necessary to their job. POLP ensures only authorized users whose identity has been verified have the necessary permissions to execute jobs within certain systems, applications, data and other assets.

Multifactor Authentication (MFA): A security feature that grants access to the user only after confirming their identity with one or more credentials in addition to their username and password. This may include a security code delivered via text or email, a security token from an authenticator app, or even a biometric identifier.

2.5. NIST vs ISO: trading off costs, complexity and certifiability of cybersecurity practices for an organisation

The CSF has three major components: **the framework core, implementation tiers, and profiles**, all designed to help you benchmark your organization's risk maturity and security posture, in order to prioritize actions, you need to take to make improvements. The framework core describes the actual controls and bones of the program, while implementation tiers illustrate an organization's security maturity level, and profiles are formed by a company's unique mix of risks, controls, and technology.

ISO 27001 is designed to help an organization operationalize cybersecurity controls they may have developed to cover particular situations, or compliance needs into full-fledged information security management systems (ISMS) and security controls.

In comparing NIST CSF vs ISO 27001, both offer robust frameworks for cybersecurity risk management. An organization seeking to become compliant with ISO 27001 standards and implement the NIST CSF framework will find them easy to integrate. Their control measures are similar, and the definitions and codes are fairly transferable across frameworks. Both frameworks offer a simple vocabulary that allows you to communicate clearly about cybersecurity issues across multidisciplinary teams and with external stakeholders. They are produced by reputable standards organizations and updated to match external trends. There are a few key differences:

- **Risk Maturity:** while ISO 27001 does not have maturity tiers, the NIST CSF provides four implementation tiers that illustrate an organization's security maturity based on adherence to NIST's guidance. Companies seeking to evaluate their security performance against industry benchmarks and elevate the maturity of their cybersecurity risk programs can use NIST's tiers to target higher levels of implementation;
- **Cost:** ISO 27001 involves a series of audits and certifications that involve a greater expense. NIST CSF is voluntary, which allows organizations to implement the standard using their preferred pace and resources;
- **Certification:** ISO 27001 offers globally recognized certification via third-party audit that can be costly but can enhance your organization's reputation as a business that stakeholders can trust. NIST CSF does not offer such certification

2.6. SCADA: Software and Hardware Perspective

Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition systems are used for the control, monitoring and analysis of processes and equipment at the industrial scale². SCADA governs both software and hardware and enables the remote operation of power systems such as solar power plants. In line with the NIST CSF 2.0 framework, the **CONVERT SCADA** control System provides a set of guidelines in order to satisfy users requirements related to cybersecurity. **In the following chapters several guidelines are mentioned in details: the following points are the foundation of system's specifications requested and committed by several customers in order to satisfied cybersecurity's recommendations.**

² Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition; systems used for the control, monitoring and analysis of processes and equipment at the industrial scale. <https://scada-international.com/>

1. Asset Inventory and documentation
2. Networking documentation
3. Hardening
4. User Account Configuration and Management
5. Antimalware Solution
6. Patching Management
7. Backup & Disaster Recovery Planning
8. CERT Services Activation

- **Asset Inventory and documentation**

Asset inventory and documentation is a mandatory step to identify and detail which components are part of each SCADA architecture. Gathering information regarding component type (including network components, PLC, RTUs, Controllers, Gateways), their function, serial numbers, respective HW/SW vendor, firmware versions, OS versions, software applications installed, version information, license information, patch level, HW/SW configuration, physical location of the assets, etc, provides a clear picture of the elements of the systems and allows to design the right processes for ensuring security. In particular for examples:

- List of Applications, utilities, scripts, configuration files, databases and all other software supplied including revisions and patches;
- Software baseline Image

- **Networking documentation**

The network must be designed in compliance with the Network Model Architecture. Accordingly, hardware features of the network need to be properly documented and identified when relevant, including for instance:

- The Remote-Control LAN;
- The Network Segregation;
- Specific services networks (such as TSO, video surveillance, etc. - only if required by the project), segmented by the rest of the network;
- The Firewall, switches and routers model/family

The following documents must be shared with the customer:

- Functional Network Schema (High-level Documentation);
- Physical Connections Schema (Detailed Documentation);
- SCADA System Data Flow;
- Complete IP Address Map;
- CP/IP protocols, ports and services required for normal operation and any other ports and services required for emergency operation;
- Network devices configuration: It includes Routing Tables, Natting Tables, Firewall rules.

- **Hardening**

SCADA Systems shall be free of all HW and SW components not required for the operation of the industrial process. On all the systems in scope, unnecessary hardware components

shall be physically disabled or removed by the commissioning team in order to avoid possible modification of its configuration performed by any malicious software. They also remove and/or disable all software components not required on the systems for the operation and maintenance of the SCADA.

• User Account Configuration and Management

User Account configuration must be based on the principles of Separation of Duties and Least privilege.

Each SCADA Computerized Systems shall be joined to Customer group policy, authentication mechanism and logs management.

These systems notably need to provide relevant documentation to ensure secure user access and minimise risks on this front:

- documentation about the User Account Configuration of all the IACS computerized systems;
- documentation about Access credentials and user Roles, including system management credentials (e.g. BIOS, firmware, management interfaces) - to be provided in confidential way;
- list of the well-known privileged local accounts removed or renamed, and the actions performed on them. For them not removed or renamed, documented reasons to have user accounts locally defined on SCADA Systems.

• Antimalware Solution

The SCADA systems shall be always protected by an Antimalware solution.

Every time it is feasible, the owner of the SCADA shall validate and install the antivirus solution of the Customer. If the use of Customer solution is not possible with the systems provided, an alternative antimalware shall be foreseen by the owner and agreed with Customer.

• Patching Management

SCADA systems shall be supplied updated to the latest security patch level available, after having performed patches validation and certification with SW vendors. When feasible, the SCADA computerized systems shall be integrated with Customer Patch Management Platform.

• Backup & Disaster Recovery Planning

The SCADA control systems provides a backup infrastructure or tool and a backup schema to ensure data and system restore in case of data corruption or system loss. In particular this procedure is based on:

- Description of Backup solution in place;
- Backup & Disaster Recovery Plan providing clear instructions on how to create, test and manage backups, and how to rebuild the systems starting from backups or images.

• CERT Services Activation

The SCADA's owners shall support Customer personnel during the Cyber Security Service Activation with Customer CERT(Computer Emergency Response Team (CERT) Services Activation) ensuring the Technical implementation activities to guarantee logs and events delivery to CERT or to other logs collectors:

- Details description regarding the relevant Security Events produced, logged and their criticality;
- Information about logs types, intermediate log collection systems, integration mechanisms and protocols used;
- Hints about pre-defined criteria for the security correlation rules to be tested and used to provide evidence regarding any anomaly or security problem related to the specific context

3. Regulatory & standards Landscape: Cyber Security for a multi actors' system

The regulatory framework for cybersecurity is evolving rapidly in Europe as the European Union adopts tools and regulations adapted to the fast-changing realities of the digital world. A crucial focus of the EU regulatory approach to cybersecurity and more generally the question of data is on the notion of data ownership and consumer safety, notably around the structuring General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) which applies far beyond the energy sector. As the energy sector is increasingly digitised, and as such increasingly subject to data exchanges, and under the threat of disruptions linked to cybersecurity. PV systems represent specific challenges in terms of cyber security and grid friendliness, owing to the nature of the technology, their decentralised scale – even for utility project – compared to the thermal generation asset that dominated the electricity system until now, or their electricity generation behaviour. Digitalisation is a key answer to the sound integration of massive share of PV in the electricity grid, and embedding cybersecurity best practices early in the deployment of PV systems ensures the long-term reliability of systems.

3.1. Regulatory Framework

The NIS2 Directive (Directive (EU) 2021/2177) establishes a framework to enhance the cybersecurity of critical sectors, including the energy industry. Its objective is to ensure a high level of security of network and information systems across the EU, addressing emerging cyber threats. Under NIS2, operators of essential services, such as operators in the solar energy supply chain, must implement robust cybersecurity measures, including risk management, incident detection and response capabilities, and reporting obligations for significant cyber incidents. Non-compliance can lead to serious fines and legal consequences. Member States must implement the NIS2 Directive by 17 October 2024.

The Cyber Resilience Act (CRA) (Regulation (EU) 2022/0272) contains requirements for manufacturers of products with digital elements. This includes most software and hardware products, including the majority of products in the solar energy supply chain. It defines mitigation and vulnerability handling measures for these products and different compliance processes, depending on the risk class of the product. The CRA has been agreed upon by lawmakers in early 2024. Its adoption is expected in H2, 2024.

The Radio Equipment Directive (RED), Directive 2014/53/EU, establishes essential safety and electromagnetic compatibility requirements before placing these products on the market. Compliance involves conducting conformity assessments and affixing the CE marking to demonstrate adherence to EU standards. The RED plays a vital role in ensuring the safety and reliability of radio equipment used in solar energy systems, contributing to the overall integrity of Europe's renewable energy infrastructure. The RED applies to various actors within the solar energy

supply chain who use radio equipment as part of their operations. This includes components such as wireless monitoring systems, communication devices, and controllers used in solar panel installations. It applies to manufacturers, importers, and distributors of such radio equipment.

The Critical Entities Resilience Directive (CER Directive), released in 2022, aims to enhance the resilience of critical entities against a wide range of threats, including natural disasters, terrorist and cyber-attacks, and sabotage. It requires EU Member States to identify critical entities that provide services essential for the maintenance of vital societal functions or economic activities. These entities are required to adopt a national strategy, carry out regular risk assessments, and enhance their resilience with guidance material, exercises, advice, and training. The directive also ensures that national authorities have the powers, resources, and means to supervise critical entities, including conducting on-site inspections and introducing penalties for non-compliance.

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), effective from May 25, 2018, is a comprehensive data privacy law enacted by the European Union (EU). It imposes obligations on organizations worldwide that target or collect data related to people in the EU. The GDPR mandates how personal data should be collected, processed, stored, and transferred, ensuring data privacy and security. Non-compliance can result in severe penalties, reaching into the tens of millions of euros.

3.2. Upcoming Regulations

Beyond existing regulatory tools, the European Union is regularly updating or introducing new regulations that strengthen its legislative toolbox and adapts it to the fast evolution of digitalisation throughout the European economy, especially in the energy sector.

3.2.1. Network Code on Cybersecurity

The Network Code on Cybersecurity (NCCS) were released in March 2024. They aim to enhance the cyber resilience of the EU's energy infrastructure. The objective of this code is to establish a recurrent process of cybersecurity risk assessments in the electricity sector. It systematically identifies entities performing digitalized processes with a critical or high impact on cross-border electricity flows, their cybersecurity risks, and the necessary mitigating measures. The code establishes a governance model aligned with existing EU legislation, notably the revised Network and Information Security Directive (NIS2). It is now subject to scrutiny by the Council and European Parliament, and the rules will enter into force once this period is over. Unlike most other mentioned regulations in section 3.1 of this document, these network codes are primarily focused on the electricity sector, and ensuring sound cross-border flow of a electricity (a key competency of the EU as the electricity market is a major component of the Internal EU market).

3.3. Standards framework

International standard frameworks are generally governed by ISO, IEC and NIST. ISO/IEC 27000 series is group of standards designed to assist organizations in improving their information security. It does so by defining the information security management system (ISMS) requirements. The ISO/IEC 27001 is the central standard, detailing requirements for establishing, implementing and maintaining ISMS. Organizations can be audited and certified against this standard.

ISO/IEC 27019 addresses the specific cybersecurity needs of the energy industry by detailing guidelines for implementing and managing security measures within the context of energy utilities. The objective is to enhance the cybersecurity of process control systems, such as SCADA, in order to protect these critical systems from cyber threats. Ensuring their confidentiality, integrity, and availability; thus, improving the overall resilience of energy infrastructure. The former version from 2017 is expected to be replaced soon for an updated one, which is currently in the Final Draft stage.

The NIST Cybersecurity Framework main purpose is to provide guidance on what organizations should do in order to manage their cybersecurity risk. The framework is designed to be adaptable for organizations of various sizes and sectors. In the energy sector, it helps companies to identify vulnerabilities and implement protective measures for process control systems and operational technology. In addition, it assists in detecting potential threats and anomalies, responding effectively to incidents, and recovering from disruptions. Therefore, companies can improve their resilience against cyber threats, ensuring the reliability of their energy operations and infrastructure.

The CIS Critical Security Controls is not a formal standard, however, are generally used as complementary best practices to assist in the implementation of cybersecurity measures effectively in the energy sector.

3.4. Impact on innovations in Supernova, cooperate standards, IoT, IECS

Cybersecurity regulations and frameworks have a significant influence in shaping innovations and cooperative activities within the industry. The threat of cyberattacks demands corporations to be more cautious in managing data access and risks. This is particularly important in the renewable energy sector, where digital interactions are essential for plant operations, where multiple SCADA systems interact directly with energy market players, transmission system operator (TSO) and distribution network operator (DNO). In addition, allowing remote network access for maintenance purposes, or establishing connections for third-party data monitoring. The potential impact of cyberattacks to these assets are significant, as these power plants are directly connected to complex grid systems, with thousands of stakeholders.

Innovations in hardware and software must not only comply with regulatory frameworks but also meet high industry standards. Cybersecurity is not only seen as an operational risk, but as well as a relevant commercial risk. In Supernova the interaction of innovations in relation to cybersecurity is highlighted in this document, mainly exemplified within the PV data space context. It is vital that research institutes, universities and industry players interact, setting of requirements necessary for a product to be compliant, thus Supernova allows direct communication among multiple players from different backgrounds.

In the context of cooperation activities, which generally involves data sharing or granting of network access to a third party, ensuring awareness and compliance of regulatory cybersecurity frameworks is essential for a trustworthy collaboration. Although such activities are usually governed by data sharing agreements (DSA) or non-disclosure agreements (NDA), the industry lacks any form of standardization or harmonization on how confidential and/or sensitive data should be handled in collaborative project. Thus, technical cooperation between new partners can become cumbersome, demanding several iterations between legal departments in order to reach a common agreement, sometimes undermining activities even before it starts.

Conclusion and recommendations

The PV sector is growing fast and digitalising rapidly, making it ever more exposed to cybersecurity risks – both as these risks are ever more present overall and as the PV sector represents an increasingly visible target for disruption as it becomes a central source of electricity generation. PV systems are also increasingly interconnected to different services, including energy storage, flexibility provisions, weather forecasting and so on. Smarter systems need to be able to cooperate easily and securely.

As highlighted throughout this document, there are many solutions and framework to design a cybersecurity programme for a PV system. All systems are defined by a comprehensive approach that aims to minimise vulnerabilities by creating a system that is – as much as possible – secure by design and able to operate while being safe from threats of disruption. Framework and design systems for cybersecurity programmes put a strong emphasis on the hardware of a system and in ensure that this segment of PV plant does not represent a vulnerability, but this attention also encompasses the hardware for bringing assets data online, and obviously the software. The comprehensive adoption of a cybersecurity framework allows to address all facets of a project. A key question for developers therefore remains: which framework to adopt?

In this document, we have highlighted two structuring frameworks of relevance for PV power plants operators when it comes to cybersecurity:

- NIST: comprehensive framework with strong synergies with SCADA systems, higher potential for flexible application according to the needs of companies and customers, that allows continuous improvement towards further degrees of risk-preparedness.
- ISO 270000: the ISO27000 set of cybersecurity standards a thorough and comprehensive set of standards that is particularly relevant to provide a certified guarantee as to a level of cybersecurity, crucial when verifiability of a framework is needed by customers or partners. Their application is however more costly, time-consuming and cumbersome as they imply specific certification and verification procedures.

On top of these two roadmaps to guarantee robust security practices, PV power plants operators in the European Union need to comply with relevant legislations, notably including the General Data Protection Regulation. Developers should select the relevant framework for designing their cybersecurity strategy, while making sure they comply with the rapidly evolving European regulatory framework, which has seen the continuous addition of new regulatory texts between 2022 and 2024.